

THE INFLUENCE OF REDUCING THE CELL SIZE TO THE NANOSCALE ON THE PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF POLYMERIC NANOCCELLULAR FOAMS.

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ABSTRACT

This study is focused on the effect of reducing the cell size to the nanoscale on the physical properties of poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) foams produced by a solid state foaming process using CO₂ as physical foaming agent.

For this purpose, several microcellular and nanocellular foams with similar relative densities have been produced and characterised. The properties that have been studied are: the glass transition temperature, the mechanical behavior at low and high strain rates, the dynamical mechanical behavior, and the thermal conductivity.

The results obtained have proved that there is a clear transition in the experimental results of the analysed properties when cell size is reduced from the micro-scale to the nano-scale.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays society is demanding light-weight materials with tailor-made properties for each application. To cover this need, one of the best solutions is the use of cellular materials due to reductions in weight, raw material, production costs, and the excellent properties (tailor-made) that can be achieved. These materials have a great present and a very promising future in important technological sectors such as automotive, aeronautical, renewable energies, construction, cushioning and packaging, biotechnology, etc.

It is well known that the properties of cellular materials depend on both the properties of the solid matrix and the characteristics of the cellular structure. Focusing on the key characteristics of the cellular structure, one of the most common strategies to improve the performance is reducing the average cell size of the foam.

The validity of this strategy was proved at MIT in the 80s with the development of microcellular foams [1]. Nowadays, one important trend in the cellular materials field is reducing the cell size from values about 10 microns (typical for microcellular materials) to values clearly below 1 micron. These materials known as nanocellular materials are very promising materials because of the expected improvement in some of their physical properties in comparison with conventional and microcellular foams [2, 3].

It is expected that nanocellular foams produced from amorphous polymers with cell sizes under the wavelength of the visible radiation could keep, up to some extent, the transparent character of the

former solid [4]. In addition, cell size reduction for low density foams will allow a significant reduction of the thermal conductivity due to the decrease of the heat conduction through the gas phase (Knudsen effect [2]). This behaviour has been proved both in aerogels [5, 6] and recently in nanocellular polymeric foams [7]. In addition, it is also expected that nanocellular materials will have better mechanical properties than conventional cellular materials or microcellular materials. It is well known the relationship between the mechanical properties of a cellular material and their cellular structure [8, 9]. Some of these properties (toughness, impact resistance, fatigue, stiffness, strength, hardness, etc.) are increased for materials with smaller cell sizes and when the material has a more homogeneous cellular structures. This effect was achieved with the development of microcellular foams [1], and it is expected that will be also found with the development of nanocellular foams [10]. Finally, with these new materials some non-expected improvements or some new effects could appear due to the dimension of the cell size and cell walls in the nanometer range. Therefore, using these novels materials it would be possible to produce products with a combination of properties that cannot be found nowadays.

However, due to the recent development of this nanocellular polymers, the works [10-13] and patents [14] in this topic are still scarce. In this work, several PMMA foams with a significant size, with homogeneous cellular structures, and with cell sizes from the micro to the nanometer range have been produced and characterized with the aim of analysing the effect of reducing the cell size up to the nanoscale on some of the key physical properties of the foams.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PART

Optically transparent poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) was kindly supplied by Altuglas-Arkema Company (France) in the form of pellets. The PMMA used presents a glass transition temperature (T_g) of 115 °C and a density (ρ) of 1180 kg/ m³.

Samples Production

PMMA pellets were first dried in vacuum (680 mm Hg) at 80 °C during 4 h. Then, they were compression molded into precursors of 155 mm x 75 mm and 4 mm in thickness using a two-hot plates press. The temperature of the press was fixed at 250 °C. The material was first molten without pressure for 9 minutes, then it was pressed under a constant pressure of 21.8 bars for another minute and finally it was cooled down under the same pressure. Transparent samples obtained showed a good surface appearance with no air bubbles inside the parts. Finally, these molded precursors were cut at the desired dimensions (depending on the test to be performed) and used for foaming.

Foaming Experiments

Foaming experiments were carried out in a high pressure vessel (model PARR 4681) provided by Parr Instrument Company, with a capacity of 1 liter and capable of operating at a maximum temperature of 350 °C and a maximum pressure of 41 MPa. The reactor is equipped with an accurate pressure pump controller (model SFT-10) provided by Supercritical Fluid Technologies Inc., and it is controlled automatically to keep the pressure at the desired values. The temperature is controlled via a CAL 3300 temperature controller. The CO₂ vessel temperature and pressure were monitored in the course of the process. Therefore, a collection of experiments were performed using the so-called solid state foaming process. This process with amorphous polymers has three stages: the saturation (under fixed gas pressure and temperature), desorption (room pressure and temperature), and foaming of the sample (at a temperature over the effective glass transition T_g). Samples were saturated at room temperature and at two different pressures, 13 MPa (to produce microcellular foams) and 31 MPa (to produce nanocellular foams) during 20 h to reach saturation. After the saturation process, the pressure inside the vessel was released. During the desorption step, the samples temperature decrease to values clearly below room temperature (adiabatic depressurization), so when samples are removed from the pressure vessel they are still non-foamed. Foaming of the samples was carried out in a thermostatic

water bath at temperatures between 25 and 60 °C and times between 40 seconds and 5 minutes. The temperatures used were lower than the glass transition temperature of PMMA because the effective glass transition temperature of plastized PMMA with CO₂ can reach values near room temperature [15] or even below room temperature in some particular conditions [16].

3 CHARACTERIZATION TECHNIQUES

Density measurements of solid and foamed PMMA samples were performed by water-displacement method, based on Archimedes' principle, using the density determination kit for an AT261 Mettler-Toledo balance. At least three measurements were carried out for each sample produced.

The cellular structure of foams samples was analyzed by means of scanning electron microscopy (model JSM 820, Jeol). Foams were frozen in liquid nitrogen and fractured to assure that the microstructure remained intact. The fractured surface was coated with gold using a sputter coater (model SCD 005, Balzers Union). Cell sizes were determined with a specific software [17] based on ImageJ/FIJI [18]. This software provides among other characteristics the average cell size, the standard deviation of the cell size distribution and the cell nucleation density N_0 (number of cells per cubic centimeter of the solid precursor) [19]:

Characteristic thermal properties of the foamed and solid materials were studied in order to analyze the effect of cell size in the glass transition temperature. A Mettler DSC822e differential scanning calorimeter previously calibrated with Indium was used.

Mechanical properties in tension at low strain rates were determined using an universal testing machine Instron model 5.500R6025. At least three specimens were tested for each kind of sample, all of them at room temperature. Tensile tests were carried out at a strain rate of 0.5 mm/ min according to ISO 527/2.

A 0.5 Joules pendulum for impact testing (Charpy, Izod, Tensile) Frank was used in order to determine the mechanical behavior at high strain rates. At least six specimens were used for each sample, all of them carried out at room temperature and performed according to ISO 179-1.

Viscoelastic behavior of foamed samples both at room temperature and as a function of temperature was analyzed using a dynamic mechanical analyzer model DMA 7 from Perkin Elmer. The experiments were performed in a three point bending configuration with a frequency of 1 Hz and a dynamic stress of 3·10⁴ KPa for foams and of 1·10⁵ KPa for the solids. A static stress of 1.2 times the value of the dynamic stress was applied in all the conducted tests.

Thermal conductivity has been measured by the Transient Plane Source (TPS) technique using a thermal conductivity mod. HDMD (hotdisk) [20]. All the measurements have been carried out at room temperature.

A polishing machine (model LaboPOI2-LaboForce3, Struers) equipped with a silicon carbide grinding paper (P 600) was used to obtain homogeneous surfaces and to remove the outer solid or dense skin of the samples. After polishing, samples had an average thickness of around 5 mm.

All the mechanical and thermal tests were conducted on samples in which the skin was previously removed.

4 RESULTS

In order to achieve similar densities between samples with cells in the micro and nanometer range,

samples saturated at 13 MPa were foamed in a thermostatic water bath at 60 °C during 40 seconds, meanwhile samples saturated at 31 MPa were foamed at 25 °C during 5 minutes. Density results for the solid, the microcellular and the nanocellular materials are summarized in Table 1. The processing parameters were finely tuned to produce foams with similar densities which make easier the analysis of the effect of the cell size of the properties.

Name	ρ (g/cm ³)
PMMA_solid	1.18
Micro PMMA foam	0.61
Nano PMMA foam	0.53

Table 1. Density results of foamed and solid samples

Cellular Structure

Characterization of the cellular structure of foamed samples has been carried out in two different planes: ZY plane and ZX plane, where Z is the thickness direction. SEM images of the foamed samples in these two planes can be observed in Figure 1. The difference between the microcellular foam (top) and the nanocellular one (bottom) is clearly observed. Both the microcellular and the nanocellular foam present very homogeneous cellular structures without important differences between planes.

Figure 1: SEM images of the cellular structure of microcellular (top) and nanocellular (bottom) PMMA foams in two different planes.

Average cell size together with cell nucleation density (N_0), and the standard deviation of the cell size distribution divided by the average cell size are summarized in Table 2. From cell nucleation density data it can be observed a difference of five orders of magnitude between foams in the micro and nanometer range.

The standard deviation divided by the average cell size provides information about the homogeneity of the cellular structure. The results obtained confirm that both microcellular and nanocellular foams present a uniform distribution, being more slightly homogeneous for foams in the micrometer range.

Name	Φ (nm)	N_0 (cells/cm ³)	Standard Deviation (SD) / Φ
Micro_ZY	11880	$7 \cdot 10^8$	0.22
Micro_ZX	11330	$8 \cdot 10^8$	0.28
Nano_ZY	345	$5 \cdot 10^{13}$	0.43
Nano-ZX	310	$7 \cdot 10^{13}$	0.33

Table 2. Cellular structure results for the microcellular (denoted as micro) and nanocellular (denoted as nano) PMMA foams.

Physical Properties

Several physical properties of microcellular and nanocellular foams with similar densities (Table 1) have been characterized. The first interesting property observed in these materials is related to the thermal properties of foamed PMMA. Figure 2 shows an appreciable increase in the glass transition temperature (measured by DSC) from 118.2 °C in the microcellular material to 124.2 °C in the nanocellular foam. This effect could be attributed to a confining effect [21, 22] due to the average cell size reduction and the increase of cell density that leads to a lower cell wall thickness. In this study, cell wall thickness of nanocellular foams is around 60 nanometers.

The same trend was also observed in the dynamic-mechanical tests (Figure 3) where the maximum of $\tan \delta$ is associated with the glass transition temperature. The nanocellular foam presents a T_g 7 °C higher than that of both the microcellular foams and the solid matrix.

Figure 2. Glass transition temperature for both PMMA solid as for PMMA microcellular and nanocellular foams respectively.

Density of foamed samples plays a main role on the mechanical behavior, due to this and in order to compare the properties of the materials under study, the mechanical properties at high and low strain rates were divided by the square of relative density (Figure 4 and Figure 5 respectively).

Figure 3. $\tan \delta$ vs temperature obtained by DMA for both PMMA solid as for PMMA microcellular and nanocellular foams.

Figure 4. Mechanical behavior at high strain rates divided by the relative density for both PMMA solid and for PMMA microcellular and nanocellular foams respectively.

Figure 5. Tensile Young modulus normalized by the square of the relative density for both PMMA solid and for PMMA microcellular and nanocellular foams respectively.

The results corresponding to the impact resistance tests (Figure 4) show that there is a clear transition in the values between microcellular and nanocellular foams. This increase of the impact resistance is related with the change in the cellular structure of the nanocellular material. Solid material presents a behavior in between microcellular and nanocellular foams.

Concerning Young's modulus results (Figure 5), both microcellular and nanocellular foams exhibit a lower value than the solid one. Nanocellular foams have a higher Young's modulus value than the microcellular ones; although in this case the difference is small. A similar trend was also obtained by measuring the storage modulus as a function of the temperature by DMA (Figure 6). As it can be observed the modulus of the nanocellular foams is higher than that of the microcellular foams in all the temperature range under study.

Figure 6. Storage modulus normalized by the square of the relative density for both PMMA microcellular and nanocellular foams.

Finally, thermal conductivity of the samples was also analyzed. Density of foamed samples also plays an important role on the thermal conductivity, and then the thermal conductivity divided by the relative density is plotted in Figure 7 to analyze the influence of cell size.

Figure 7. Thermal conductivity measurements divided by the relative density for both PMMA solid and for PMMA microcellular and nanocellular foams respectively.

These results show again that there is a clear transition in the values of the thermal conductivity between microcellular and nanocellular foams. This significant reduction of the thermal conductivity is due to a combination of the Knudsen effect and an increment of the solid phase tortuosity [7].

5 CONCLUSIONS

The experimental results have demonstrated that nanocellular polymeric foams produced by the solid state foaming process from neat PMMA, present a significant improvement in several physical properties due to the modified cellular structure and/or the confinement of the polymer matrix. The mechanical behavior at high strain rates of nanocellular foams is clearly increased in comparison with microcellular foams; in addition a slightly increase of the Young's modulus has also been detected. The glass transition temperature of foams in the nanometer range is also increased and the thermal conductivity is reduced in comparison with microcellular foams. Some of the potential benefits of nanocellular foams in comparison with microcellular have been showed in this paper.

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